

SOCIAL-PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF A MODERN TEACHER

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Annotation: In this article, the personality of the modern pedagogue and his image, the teacher requirements for a person, his social, pedagogical, psychological characteristics and what a modern teacher should be are explained. Pedagogical skill teacher issues such as an important component of quality, techniques of working with students are also covered.

Key words: modern teacher, psychology, psychological characteristics, social characteristics, pedagogical skill, pedagogical communication, creative, orator, initiative.

INTRODUCTION

How should a modern teacher be? From the first days of independence since then, many pedagogues and psychologists have expressed their opinions on this problem came out with their comments. National tradition of teachers' professional skills and further improvement based on our traditions and values, to form their pedagogical activities at the level of modern requirements methodical manuals, recommendations have appeared. This is still the case today scientific research on the problem, scientific research is ongoing.

By the 21st century, the role of the teacher is becoming more and more sophisticated. Now global changes, science and technology and information and communication the daily development of technology requires a high level of skill from the teacher, requires strong will, psychological strength, deep knowledge and reasoning. Today's teacher, along with the knowledge of his specialty, Pedagogical and psychological knowledge, as well as special in various fields of science having knowledge, professional training, possessing high moral qualities, is a person working in educational institutions. From this point of view, the present The following duties and responsibilities are required of teachers on a daily basis:

- A teacher is first of all an educator who feels responsible, an experienced speaker, is a promoter of culture and enlightenment.

- The teacher can naturally love students, his affection, feelings students should be able to connect with their inner world at every moment, and deserve their love and respect.

- The teacher takes the changes that are happening in the social life of the society deep understanding of the essence of ongoing socio-economic reforms and to them evaluate objectively and provide correct, reasonable information to students in this regard should take.

- Science, technology and information-communication of a modern teacher it is required to be aware of the innovations and achievements of technologies. The role of the teacher and his tasks, how much attention is paid by society and the public to the work of educating the young generation importance is determined.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In the current situation, the society's demands on the school are increasing day by day is increasing, and it is the task of the teacher to correctly solve these requirements in practice depends.

A modern school teacher performs a number of tasks. Teacher - is the organizer of the learning process in the classroom. A teacher is needed for students during classes, in additional classes, and at the same time in extracurricular situations One of the sources of knowledge in giving advice, most teachers are class leader performing their duties, they are the organizers of the educational process.

A modern teacher cannot be a social psychologist. That's why for the ability to establish mutual relations between teachers, children it is necessary to know how to use socio-psychological mechanisms in his team. As a member of the school's pedagogical team, the teacher directly participates in the coordination of school life activities, works in methodological associations of various subject teachers and class leaders, performs assignments. As each teacher reads lectures and conducts conversations in front of parents and the public, he is also a promoter of pedagogical knowledge, and because of such a large number of tasks, the society puts teachers before them. requirements are clear.

The modern teacher's model represents a solid combination of the teacher's personal qualities, professional competence and individual style of skill, which ensures efficiency, activity and communication convenience in a single educational environment.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

It is known that pedagogical activity is one of the most complex areas of human labor.

The most important of the requirements imposed by the society is focused on the personality of the teacher and the qualities related to his profession.

The most important qualities of a teacher are:

- it consists of the teacher's loyalty to his Motherland, love of children, desire to educate them in the spirit of humanity, love of his country, mother tongue, history and culture of his people, living in the idea of independence of his state;

-high sense of social responsibility;

- instilling in children high goals in terms of nobility, intelligence, insight, piritual purity, spirituality and enlightenment;

- self-restraint, patience, endurance, perseverance.

The main demands of the society to the teacher are as follows:

- to know the essence of spiritual and educational upbringing of a person, the ideology of national renaissance and universal wealth, to raise children in the spirit of loyalty to the ideals of independence, to love their homeland, nature and family;

- to have wide knowledge, to be aware of various knowledge;

- to have deep knowledge of youth and pedagogical psychology, social psychology and pedagogy, youth physiology and school hygiene;

- to have a solid knowledge of the subject he teaches, to be aware of the new achievements and shortcomings of the world science in his profession and field;

-acquisition of educational methodology in education;

-creative approach to his work;

-knowing children, being able to understand their inner world;

- to have pedagogical techniques (logic, speech, expressive means of education) and pedagogical tactics;

- constantly improving his knowledge and pedagogical skills;

- The teacher must have deep and thorough knowledge of his specialty, master the integration of all disciplines, and conduct continuous scientific research on himself.

- The teacher should thoroughly know the basics of pedagogy and psychology, organize educational activities taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students.

- The teacher should be able to effectively use the most effective modern forms, methods and tools of education and training in his professional pedagogical activities.

- A teacher is a creator, an initiator of educational activities and a person responsible for the future of the young generation.

- In the course of his professional activity, the teacher must master the rules of high-level pedagogical skill, communicative ability, pedagogical technique (speech, face, hand, foot and body movements, mime, pantomime, tact).

It is necessary for the teacher to have speech culture, his speech should reflect the following features: it should be free of various dialect words and expressed only in literary language; the teacher's speech should be simple, fluent and understandable; should be able to use wise words, phrases and proverbs, proverbs and quotations

appropriately. Slang (words specific to certain professions or fields), barbarism (inappropriate use of words specific to other nations in a speech in the language of a particular nation), vulgarism (insults, insults words) and to be free of informal words such as conciliarism (the use of formal words in inappropriate situations).

- First of all, a teacher should be thoughtful, accurate, able to correctly assess any pedagogical situation and independently manage to eliminate existing conflicts.

Based on the above requirements, a modern pedagogue should be a highly cultured, eloquent, student-loving, kind, creative, well-versed in his subject, a psychologist, capable of using modern techniques. The teacher is the engineer of the child's heart.

- **A teacher as an educator should know the following requirements:** to know the essence of the ideology of national revival and universal wealth in the spiritual and educational upbringing of a person, to raise children in the spirit of loyalty to the ideals of independence, to love their Motherland, nature and family;

- to be aware of various knowledge, along with thorough knowledge of professional knowledge;

- perfect knowledge of youth pedagogical psychology, pedagogy and psychology, youth physiology, educational work methodology, school hygiene;

- to be constantly aware of the latest achievements in world science, educational technology, computer and information technologies, and news of his profession;

- improving skills and qualifications in educational methods; creative approach to his profession;

- to have pedagogical technique (logic, expressive means of speech education) and pedagogical tact;

- constantly improving his knowledge and pedagogical skills.

Every teacher must strive to fully meet these requirements. In addition to the demands of the society, the teacher should not forget what the people around him, the school administration, colleagues, students and their parents expect from him.

The fact that the teacher sees something from his work is important in itself, and this observation, although it comes to the demands placed on the teacher by society, has its own characteristics. But these requirements may not always match. According to research conducted by psychologists, public education departments and school principals have different assessments of the importance of certain qualities of a teacher. For example, if the heads of the public education departments demand that the student first of all know his subject well and master the teaching methodology perfectly, the school principals put such demands on the teacher in the third place. At the same time, heads of public education departments do not pay much attention to how important it is for teachers to know how to communicate with students, parents,

and the school, and school principals attach such qualities to the personality of the teacher. they put in the first place among the requirements.

Ethical qualities of a teacher.

The teaching profession is one of the most difficult, but at the same time proud and noble professions. The teacher equips students with the system of scientific knowledge included in the school curriculum, shapes their worldview, develops memory, attention and imagination, teaches them to think creatively, educates their emotions and will, develops their abilities, and shapes their character.

The teacher systematically conducts all his educational work, subordinating it day by day to the main goal - "to educate a new person who harmoniously embodies spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection." Leads.

The teacher does not control the formation of the student's personality only in classes and extracurricular activities. The teacher, with his personal example, appearance and behavior, influences the students with his inner spiritual qualities, sometimes without realizing it. It remains their ideal. A person often chooses his life path under the influence of his favorite teacher.

N. D. Levitov in his manual of child psychology pedagogical psychology cites the following as important pedagogical skills:

1. The ability to impart knowledge to teachers is achieved primarily by presenting the material clearly, concisely and interestingly.
2. Understanding the student.
3. Independence and creativity of thinking.
4. Responsiveness or quick and clear understanding.
5. Organizational skills, which are expressed in accurate planning and proper use of time, constant supervision of students, ability to distinguish and organize class activists, and the skills of cohesiveness of the class team.

CONCLUSION

Modern times place high demands on the professional training of teachers and their personal and professional maturity (psychology):

a) at all stages of the socio-historical development of our country, the personality of the teacher has a high social position and is honored as an example of ethnic consciousness and thinking of the people. A modern teacher is supposed to occupy such a high social position.

b) according to the analyzes of scientific psychology, education and training is a national-ethnic phenomenon according to its form, content and essence, and it embodies the consciousness, views, and values of the people. Naturally, the ethnopsychology of each nation and the ideal of the nation will be realized by the teacher through the education and training of his nation.

c) effective adaptation of a modern teacher to professional activities requires perfect mastery of the specific features of modern teaching methods, strict adherence to the principles of education and upbringing, professional knowledge, personal and it is determined by the fact that he embodies professional qualities and can use them rationally in his professional activities.

d) In the process of professional training of a modern teacher, the set of psychological-pedagogical educational effects that the teacher needs to acquire is compatible with the evolution of moral, social-legal and production labor standards specific to this ethnic community, and the psychological-pedagogical level of the students. It is necessary to take into account the possibilities of adapting to secrets.

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